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PROSPECTS FOR LEAVING THE POPULATION OUT OF POVERTY

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Abstract: This article examines and analyzes the prospects for lifting the population out of poverty, real total income per capita, average nominal monthly wage, average income of each family, poverty level indicators in the Samarkand region in 2023, family businesses in the Narpay district.

Key words: Poverty, real income, average income, poverty level, family business entities, sector.

Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada aholini qashshoqlikdan chiqarish istiqbollari, aholi jon boshiga real jami daromadlar, o'rtacha nominal oylik ish haqi, har bir oilaning o'rtacha daromadi, Samarqand viloyatida 2023-yilda qashshoqlik darajasi ko'rsatkichlari, Narpay tumanidagi oilaviy tadbirkorlik masalalari o'rganilib, tahlil etilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Qashshoqlik, real daromad, o'rtacha daromad, qashshoqlik darajasi, oilaviy tadbirkorlik subyektlari, sektor.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассмотрены и проанализированы перспективы вывода населения из бедности, реальный совокупный доход на душу населения, средняя номинальная месячная заработная плата, средний доход каждой семьи, показатели уровня бедности в Самаркандской области в 2023 году, субъекты семейного предпринимательства и в Нарпайском районе.

Ключевые слова: Бедность, реальный доход, средний доход, уровень бедности, субъекты семейного бизнеса, сектор.

In the message of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan to the Oliy Majlis on January 24, 2020, the fight against poverty was identified as a priority task of our economic development policy.

"Reducing poverty means awakening the spirit of entrepreneurship among the population, the full realization of a person's inner strength and potential, and the implementation of a comprehensive economic and social policy to create new jobs," the appeal says.

According to the laws of economics, "Poverty begets poverty." This process occurs for several reasons. First, low-income countries cannot spend enough money on quality education and healthcare, and poor people cannot escape poverty because they cannot afford quality education and healthcare.

Secondly, as the incomes of the poor decline, the capacity of the consumer market decreases proportionately, and as a result, the demand for industrial goods, agricultural products and especially services decreases. This, in turn, slows down economic development, reduces budget revenues and reduces the possibility of social support for the poor, creating a closed process. Third, in most cases the worldview of the poor is different from that of people with higher incomes. For the reasons stated above, they are less likely to produce creative and enterprising people. Additionally, crime rates tend to be higher among poorer families. In other words, the factors that cause poverty hinder the development of human potential in the country, the development of productive forces and economic activity of the population.

As a result of measures aimed at reducing poverty in Uzbekistan over the past three years, real total income per capital 43.9 percent, average monthly nominal wage is 79.7 percent or in 2019, it increased from 1293.8 thousand soums to 2324.5 thousand soums in 2016.

According to the results of a household survey conducted as part of the World Bank project "Listening to Citizens of Uzbekistan," the average monthly income of a low-income household for January-March 2020 is

about 1.5 million soums. increased. It should be noted that the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev raised the problem of eliminating poverty in Uzbekistan as a strategic task. The government is making great efforts to solve this problem. In particular, the country has created the necessary institutions to combat poverty. First of all, this determines the creation of the Ministry of Economic Development and Poverty Alleviation and state policy to combat poverty.

Programs are also being implemented to improve the living conditions of the population and improve rural areas. In particular, thanks to the implementation of the Prosperous Village program, the living conditions of 1.7 million rural residents have improved. In 2019 alone, 6.1 trillion soums, equivalent to 600 million US dollars, were allocated for the implementation of the "Prosperous Village" and "Prosperous Mahalla" programs. However, despite the results achieved, now in Uzbekistan

More than 400,000 families need to improve their housing conditions (according to World Bank criteria, as of October 2015, the World Poverty Rate includes those earning less than US\$1.9 per day). The share of the informal sector in the labor market is 40-50 percent. However, only 23 percent of poor households receive social benefits.

Uzbekistan is one of the socially oriented countries. In such countries, the participation of the state in the life of society is very important and involves the implementation of its social obligations to its citizens on a large scale. This creates the need for state support for socially vulnerable sections of society. Strong social policy means the distribution of social benefits by government institutions in favor of the least protected and most vulnerable members of society. Unlike many other countries, Uzbekistan has been pursuing a strong social policy in recent years. In other words, it can be noted that Uzbekistan has chosen a model of public policy that is truly compatible with the concept of social justice. When creating a register of poor families, popularly known as the "Iron Register," the problems of socially vulnerable segments of the population were also taken into account based on a door-to-door survey of poor families. This register became the basis of a targeted program to reduce poverty and improve the well-being of the population by industry. Unsolved problems at the local level that were of vital importance to the population were transferred to the regional or republican level.

Table 1: Poverty level indicators in Samarkand region in 2023

№	Name of regions	Total number of families	On practice		Expected by the end of 2023	
			Number of poor families	Poverty level (in percentages)	Number of poor people	Poverty rate (percentage)
	Total	997 116	139 596	14,0	504 691	12,0
1	Samarkand c	159 348	10 604	6,7	33 949	6,5
2	Kattakurgan c	23 926	2 678	11,2	9 324	9,8
3	Akdarya	38 588	6 043	15,7	23 568	13,7
4	Bulungur	45 205	6 964	15,4	25 077	12,4
5	Jomboy	41 194	6 166	15,0	24 620	13,1
6	Ishtikhan	60 744	9 829	16,2	35 899	13,0
7	Kattakurgan	68 185	9 150	13,4	34 384	11,7
8	Kushrabot	29 588	4 408	14,9	18 444	13,0
9	Narpay	50 006	7 764	15,5	30 870	13,5
10	Payarik	62 396	11 304	18,1	42 035	15,3
11	Pakhtachi	43 110	6 758	15,7	20 928	13,8
12	Pastdargom	85 108	15 344	18,0	57 155	14,9
13	Samarkand	71 923	5 348	7,4	17 684	6,5
14	Nurobod	36 886	6 084	16,5	20 383	12,5
15	Urgut	127 586	25 272	19,8	89 202	16,0
16	Taylok	53 323	5 880	11,0	21 169	9,6

According to data on the poverty level in the Samarkand region for 2023, there are currently 139,596 poor families in the region. This is 14% of the total population of the region. According to this indicator, 7,756 families live in the Narpai district. This is 15.5% of the total number of families in the district.

In particular, since last year, important steps have been taken in this direction in our country. In particular, in accordance with Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers No. 308 of April 13, 2019, the information system

“Unified Register of Social Protection” is being launched, which provides a transparent, real-time assessment of the needs of families. and the level of compliance of applicants with established criteria.

The next important step in this direction was the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On additional measures to automate procedures for the provision of state social services and assistance to the population” dated August 4 of this year. According to the decision, from September 1 of this year, consideration of applications for the assignment of social payments and procedures for their assignment will be carried out in stages through the information system “Unified Register of Social Protection”, which is an integral part of the “Electronic Government” system and will be implemented in all regions of the republic by the end of this year. The main goals of introducing this system are the widespread introduction of modern information and communication technologies into the social protection system, the creation of a unified system for the provision of state social services and assistance to the needy segments of the population. social protection.

As of January 1, 2023, the number of registered family enterprises in the Narpai district is 235, of which 228 are active, 7 are inactive, the share of inactive among registered is 2.9%.

The district’s share in the total number of operating family enterprises in the region is 3.3%, for every 100 families there are 0.5 units. Their number is significantly lower than the regional average (422). In other words, in terms of family business development indicators, it ranks 8th in the region (Table 1).

The distribution of the number of family enterprises operating in the Narpai district by economic sector is as follows: 14 in agriculture, forestry and fishing, 55 in industry, 4 in construction, 119 in trade, 1 in the field of transport and storage, 27 in the field of accommodation and food. services, information and communications – 1, healthcare and social services – 2, other sectors – 12.

Also, the share of inactive family enterprises among registered ones is 2.9%, of which the highest figure corresponds to 50% in the field of transportation and storage and 11.1% in the field of accommodation and food services.

According to the classification of family business development in the Narpai district, this is a medium-level territory of the “yellow” category. The role of family businesses in the socio-economic development of this area is insufficient. In this area there are almost no family business entities in the service sector, such as information and communication and social services. Therefore, when determining additional measures of regional programs for a given district, it is advisable to give priority to lending projects in the service sector within the framework of the “Every Family is an Entrepreneur” program. It is also proposed to develop a clearly planned “road map” for the transition from the “yellow” category to the “green” category.

The state of development of family entrepreneurship in the 57 MFG district differs sharply from each other. This can be seen in the table below (Table 2).

Table 2: Number of family businesses in Narpai district (as of January 1, 2023)¹

Name of regions	Number of registered family businesses	Status of family business activity		Share of inactive people among registered users, %	Founded in January-October 2022.	Completed January-October 2022
		Active	Inactive			
Narpay	235	228	7	2,9	197	9
Samarqand	7345	6956	421	5,3	5709	7345

Table 3: Level of development of family entrepreneurship in the Narpai district by industry and MFG (as of January 1, 2023)

№	Sector	Name of regions	Number of families	Number of families involved in family business		MFY category
				General	Percent, %	
1	2	3	4	5	6 = [5] * 100 % / [4]	7 = 6 = (20.0 – 100) – “green”; (10.0–19.0) – “yellow”; (0.0-9.0) – “red”
1	1	“Dedan”	862	78	9,0	“red”
2	1	“Do’stlik”	1341	232	17,3	“yellow”
3	1	“Iymon”	921	9	1,0	“red”
4	1	“Ipak yo’li”	864	94	11,0	“yellow”
5	1	“Istiqlol”	810	27	3,3	“red”

¹ It is compiled based on data from the Samarkand Regional Statistics Department.

№	Sector	Name of regions	Number of families	Number of families involved in family business		MFY category
				General	Percent, %	
1	2	3	4	5	6 = [5] * 100 % / [4]	7 = 6 = (20.0 – 100) – “green”; (10.0–19.0) – “yellow”; (0.0-9.0) – “red”
6	1	“Qoziyoqli”	1203	57	4,7	“red”
7	1	“Qozikent”	789	22	2,8	“red”
8	1	“Mustaqillik”	944	31	3,3	“red”
9	1	“Navro‘z”	813	17	2,1	“red”
10	1	“Nug‘ay”	725	20	2,8	“red”
11	1	“Olti O‘g‘il”	645	22	3,4	“red”
12	1	“Salovat”	680	462	67,9	“green”
13	1	“Sarbozor”	760	421	55,4	“green”
14	1	“Tortuvli”	1405	16	1,1	“red”
15	1	“Turon”	1034	35	3,4	“red”
16	1	“O‘zbekiston”	1207	35	2,9	“red”
17	1	“Umid”	641	11	1,7	“red”
18	1	“Yangiariq”	918	17	1,9	“red”
19	2	“Beklar”	786	44	5,6	“red”
20	2	“Birlik”	930	2	0,2	“red”
21	2	“Obihayot”	1015	64	6,3	“red”
22	2	“Ravot Olchin”	905	16	1,8	“red”
23	2	“Soxibkor”	725	17	2,3	“red”
24	2	“Tepaqo‘rg‘on”	915	36	3,9	“red”
25	2	“Haqiqat”	961	10	1,0	“red”
26	2	“O‘zbekkenti”	619	6	1,0	“red”
27	2	“Xo‘jakarzon”	862	18	2,0	“red”
28	2	“Charxin”	701	23	3,3	“red”
29	2	“Chorbog‘”	682	24	3,5	“red”
30	3	Amur Temur	619	6	1,0	“red”
31	3	“Bo‘ston”	565	10	1,8	“red”
32	3	“Guliston”	1125	3	0,3	“red”
33	3	“Islomobod”	710	18	2,5	“red”
34	3	“Ko‘k ota”	812	35	4,3	“red”
35	3	“Oq oltin”	1115	17	1,5	“red”
36	3	“Tinchlik”	619	6	1,0	“red”
37	3	“Toshko‘prik”	802	22	2,8	“red”
38	3	“Xo‘jaqo‘rg‘on”	1005	22	2,2	“red”
39	3	“Yangiobod”	790	39	4,9	“red”
40	4	Alisher Navoiy	575	9	1,6	“red”
41	4	“Ahillik”	710	8	1,1	“red”
42	4	“Barkamol”	771	36	4,7	“red”
43	4	“Baxt”	512	8	1,6	“red”
44	4	“Bolg‘ali”	983	9	1,0	“red”
45	4	“Zirabuloq”	619	9	1,5	“red”
46	4	Islom Shoir	636	84	13,2	“yellow”
47	4	“Mang‘it”	1094	16	1,5	“red”

№	Sector	Name of regions	Number of families	Number of families involved in family business		MFY category
				General	Percent, %	
1	2	3	4	5	$6 = [5] * 100 \% / [4]$	$7 = 6 = (20.0 - 100) -$ "green"; (10.0-19.0) - "yellow"; (0.0-9.0) - "red"
48	4	"Muqumiy"	620	14	2,3	"red"
49	4	"Mushkent"	620	2	0,3	"red"
50	4	"Narpay"	1436	12	1,0	"red"
51	4	"Nog'araxona"	750	98	13,0	"yellow"
52	4	Farovon	616	5	1,0	"red"
53	4	"Oqtosh"	314	23	7,3	"red"
54	4	"Tepa"	927	76	8,2	"red"
55	4	"Totkent"	671	198	29,5	"green"
56	4	"Xalqabod"	579	3	0,5	"red"
57	4	"Chaykal"	1187	94	7.9	"red"

Note. Each of the MFGs was divided into "green", "yellow" and "red" regions depending on the level of development of the family business. In this case, the main criterion was the level of coverage of family businesses in the neighborhood. According to it, high (20.0 and above) is "green", medium (10.0-19.0 percent) is "yellow" and low (from 0.0 to 9.0 percent) is "red" category, classified to MFY.

If we calculate the impact of family entrepreneurship on the economy of the area using the Pareto method (80/20), then MFGs with 20% of family entrepreneurship can provide the area with 80% of the economic growth that can be achieved through all of them. Based on this, the state of development of family entrepreneurship in 57 district gatherings of citizens of the Narpai district has been classified for 2022. At the same time, based on the obtained rating score, a classification of MFY into "green", "yellow" and "red" categories was developed (Table 3).

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